

Terpenoid Part LXVII : Synthesis of dl-Tagetonol

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Synthesis of dl-tagetonol has been accomplished by the Grignard reaction of vinyl magnesium bromide on 6-methyl-4,4-ethylenedioxy hept-2-one (IV) and deketalisation. The compound (IV) was obtained from the β -ketosulphoxide (III) by reduction with amalgamated aluminium.

IN continuation of our studies¹⁻³ employing β -ketosulphoxide as the key intermediate for the preparation of appropriate ketones and diketones which can be converted into desired terpenic compounds, we wish to report the synthesis of (\pm)tagetonol.

The acyclic keto alcohol (+)tagetonol has been isolated from Japanese *Ho-leaf oil*, obtained from the leaves and small twigs of the young plants of *Ho-Sho tree*, as a minor constituent⁴. On the basis of its relationship to tagetones and tagetenones and its spectral data, formulation (I) has been proposed for its structure⁴.

The sequence of reactions employed for the synthesis of tagetonol are depicted below.

-Sequence of Reactions Leading to the Formation of dl-Tagetonol

Ethyl 5-methyl-3,3-ethylenedioxyhexanoate⁵ (II) was prepared by carbethoxylation of isobutyl methyl ketone using the conditions employed by Soloway and La Forge⁶ for the preparation of ethyl- β -oxocaprylate and subsequent protection of the keto group by ketalisation with ethyleneglycol in benzene⁵. The ketal ester (II) on treatment with methyl sulphanyl carbanion⁷ in anhydrous tetrahydrofuran under nitrogen atmosphere afforded the β -ketosulphoxide (III) in good yield. This compound showed the

presence of sulphur through Lassaigne's test. I.R. spectrum of β -ketosulphoxide (III) showed prominent bands at 1710 cm^{-1} (carbonyl), 1035 cm^{-1} (ketal and sulphanyl bands superimposed). The compound (III) was then reduced with amalgamated aluminium in aqueous tetrahydrofuran to obtain 6-methyl-4,4-ethylenedioxy hept-2-one (IV). The absence of sulphur in compound (IV) was checked by negative Lassaigne's test. The ketal ketone (IV) was subjected to Grignard reaction⁸ with vinyl magnesium bromide in THF, which resulted in the formation of 3,7-dimethyl-5,5-ethylenedioxy octen-3-ol (V). I.R. spectrum showed prominent bands at 3450 cm^{-1} (hydroxy) and 1035 cm^{-1} (ketal). The ketal alcohol (V) was then deprotected with aqueous hydrochloric acid⁹ in acetone to obtain 3,7-dimethyl-3-hydroxy octene-5-one (I). I.R. (ν_{max}) 3480 cm^{-1}

(hydroxy), 1710 cm^{-1} (carbonyl), 3080, 1650, 915 cm^{-1} (vinyl methylene), 2950, 1810, 1440, 1360, 1165, 1110, 1070, 990 and 740 cm^{-1} . N.M.R. (δ ppm), 0.93 (6H, 2 methyl), 1.3 (3H, methyl near OH), 6.1-4.85 (3H, ABC type of vinyl proton), 2.35-1.8 (6H, methylene, methine and O-H proton).

Spectral data of our synthesised product are in good agreement with the spectral data reported for natural tagetonol⁴.

Experimental

Boiling points are uncorrected. I.R. spectra (thin liquid films) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Infra-red having sodium chloride optics and N.M.R. spectra on solutions (Ca 10%) in carbon tetrachloride using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard at 60 MHz.

6-Methyl-4,4-ethylenedioxy-1-methyl sulphinyl-hept-2-one (III) :

Methyl sulphinyl carbanion was prepared from sodium hydride (2.22 g.) and DMSO (22 ml.) under nitrogen atmosphere. An equal volume of dry THF was added and the contents were cooled in an ice bath. Ethyl-5-methyl-3,3-ethylenedioxy hexanoate (II, 5.0 g.) was then added dropwise with stirring over a period of 10 min. The ice bath was removed and the stirring continued for an hour more at room temperature. The reaction mixture was cooled to 0°, diluted with ice cold water, acidified with calculated amount of hydrochloric acid (9.2 ml) at 0° and extracted with chloroform. The extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent evaporated to obtain β -ketosulphoxide (III, 4.7 g.) as a viscous oil. It gave positive test of sulphur. No attempt was made to isolate this compound and was used as such for further reaction.

6-Methyl-4,4-ethylenedioxy hept-2-one(IV) :

To the well stirred solution of the β -ketosulphoxide (III, 6.2 g.) in aqueous tetrahydrofuran (372 ml., 10%), was added freshly prepared small pieces of aluminium amalgam (aluminium foil 6.89 g.; 2% aqueous HgCl₂, 600 ml.) and heated at 65° for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was then filtered and the residual solid washed many times with THF. The combined filtrate was concentrated to remove most of the THF and the residue was extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water and the solvent evaporated to leave an oil which was chromatographed over alumina with pet. ether-benzene (4 : 1) as the eluent. Fractionation of the above product under vacuum provided the ketal ketone (IV, 2.4 g.), b.p. 85°-100°/5-6 mm. (Found : C, 64.37; H, 9.47. C₁₀H₁₈O₃ requires C, 64.51; H, 9.67%).

3,7-Dimethyl-5,5-ethylenedioxy octen-3-ol(V) :

To the Grignard reagent, prepared from vinyl bromide (2.4 g.), magnesium (0.51 g.) in dry THF

(200 ml.) was added dropwise the ketone (IV, 1.4 g.) in THF (10 ml.) in the cold. After standing overnight, the reaction mixture was decomposed with saturated solution of ammonium chloride. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous phase extracted with ether (3×100 ml.). The total THF ether extract was dried, solvent removed and the residue upon distillation under vacuum afforded the ketal alcohol (V, 0.96 g.) in 60% yield, b.p. 100°-10°/6-7 mm. (Found : C, 67.00; H, 10.11. C₁₂H₂₂O₃ requires C, 67.29; H, 10.28%).

3,7-Dimethyl-3-hydroxy octen-5-one (I) :

The ketal (V, 0.9 g.) was mixed with acetone (16 ml.) and aqueous hydrochloric acid (4 ml., 10%) and stirred for 3 hr. at room temperature. The solution was saturated with sodium chloride and the product taken up in ether. The ether extract was dried (anhyd. Na₂SO₄), solvent removed and the residue upon distillation under vacuum provided the keto-alcohol (I, 0.4 g.) in 57% yield, b.p. 89°-90°/6-7 mm. η_D^{25} 1.4400. (Found : C, 70.61; H, 10.39. C₁₀H₁₈O₂ requires, C, 70.59; H, 10.59%).

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References

- O. P. VIG, R. C. ANAND and K. L. MATTA, *Current Sci.*, 1970, **39**, 229.
- O. P. VIG, B. VIG and J. C. KAPUR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 1078.
- O. P. VIG, J. M. SEHGAL, M. M. MAHAJAN and S. D. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 887.
- T. YOSHIDA, S. MURAKI, H. KAWAMURA and A. KAMATSU, *Agr. Biol.Chem.*, 1969, **33**, 343; *Chem. Abs.*, 1969, **71**, 50242s.
- O. P. VIG, R. C. ANAND, G. L. KAD and J. M. SEHGAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 999.
- S. B. SOLOWAY and F. B. LAFORGE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2627.
- E. J. COREY and M. CHAYKOVSKY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 1639.
- E. DEMOLE and F. LEDERER, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1968, 1128.
- R. F. CHURCH and R. E. IRLAND, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 17.